

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for GALC (UniProt ID: P54803) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

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Abstract

The galactosylceramidase protein, encoded by the *GALC* gene and referred to here as GALC, is a lysosomal hydrolase responsible for breaking down galactolipids. It is implicated in various neurological diseases. Here we have characterized six GALC commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

P54803, *GALC*, GALC, Galactocerebrosidase, Galactosylceramidase, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

GALC is a lysosomal hydrolase that catalyzes the hydrolysis of galactolipids. The protein contains three domains: a central triosephosphate isomerase (TIM) barrel involved in substrate binding, a β -sandwich domain, and a lectin domain (1). The 80 kDa GALC precursor is delivered to the lysosome via the trans-Golgi network or indirectly via secretion and re-internalization (2). Once in the lysosome, the precursor GALC is cleaved into two an N-terminal 50 kDa form and a C-terminal 30 kDa form (3, 4). In myelinated cells, GALC catalyze the hydrolysis of the myelin associated galactosylceramide. A deficiency in GALC results in myelination failure in both central and peripheral nervous systems, leading to Krabbe disease, a rare autosomal recessive neurodegenerative disorder (5). GALC has also been associated with Parkinson's disease, with variants potentially affecting protein expression and enzymatic activity (6).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (7). It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein (7). Here we characterized six commercial GALC antibodies, selected and donated by participant antibody manufacturers, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of GALC properties and function.

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (8) and in Table 3 of this data note (7).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cell lines (9). In the absence of commercially available KO cell lines, siRNA technology can be employed to knockdown (KD) the target gene (10, 11). To determine which cell line demonstrates high expression of GALC and thus be appropriate for KD, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify cell lines that express the target at levels greater than 2.5 \log_2 (transcripts per million "TPM"+1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (12). OCUM-1 expresses the GALC transcript at 5.8 TPM+1 and was therefore identified as a suitable cell line to use here. A non-targeting control siRNA pool was used to treat OCUM-1 control (ctrl) cells, while GALC was KD using a pool of siRNA targeting this gene.

To screen the six antibodies by western blot, ctrl and *GALC* KD protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with all six *GALC* antibodies in parallel (Figure 1). The precursor form of *GALC* was detected at ~74 kDa with two antibodies. In addition, A23229** detects the N-terminal cleaved form of *GALC* at ~50 kDa and GTX101197 the C-terminal cleaved form at ~26 kDa. Differential expression of *GALC* in various cell types (Table 1) was also assessed by western blot (Figure 2) using these two antibodies.

We then assessed the capability of the six antibodies to capture *GALC* from OCUM-1 protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 3). For the immunoblot step, two specific *GALC* antibodies were used following an IP. A23229 was used in IP with primary antibodies expected to detect the N-terminal region of *GALC*, as indicated by the manufacturer's datasheet, while GTX101197 was used with primary antibodies expected to react with the C-terminal region (Figure 3).

For immunofluorescence, the six antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, OCUM-1 WT and *GALC* KD cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the *GALC* antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KD cells were imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 4). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KD cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis (7).

In conclusion, we have screened six *GALC* commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human OCUM-1 WT and *GALC* KD cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (12). High-quality antibodies that successfully detect *GALC* were identified. Researchers who wish to study *GALC* in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available GALC antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in GALC, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. GALC experts are invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results. Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (7). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (13, 14).

To knockdown *GALC*, OCUM-1 cells were treated three times with the ON-TARGETplus Human *GALC* siRNA (Horizon Discovery, cat. number L-011038-00-0005). OCUM-1 ctrl cells were treated with the ON-TARGETplus Non-targeting Control Pool (Horizon Discovery, cat. number D-001810-10). Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 13778030) was used to transfect the siRNA following the manufacturer's protocol.

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are from Proteintech, cat. number RGAR001 and RGAM001, respectively. CoraLite Plus-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies are from Proteintech, cat. number RGAR003 and RGAM003, respectively. Peroxidase-conjugated Protein A for IP detection is from Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291.

Antibody screening by western blot

OCUM-1 WT and *GALC* KD cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000 x *g* for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three

washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

OCUM-1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 0.8 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~18 h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. Protein A:HRP was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.5 µg/ml.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

OCUM-1 WT and *GALC* KD cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. WT and KD cells were plated on a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary *GALC* antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade

only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (15). Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank -GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
JCRB Cell Bank	JCRB0192	CVCL_3084	OCUM-1	WT
ATCC	CRL-1682	CVCL_0152	AsPC-1	WT
ATCC	CRL-1837	CVCL_3881	SU.86.86	WT
ATCC	HTB-186	CVCL_1167	Daoy	WT
ATCC	CCL-225	CVCL_0292	HCT-15	WT
ATCC	HTB-22	CVCL_0031	MCF7	WT
ATCC	HTB-96	CVCL_0042	U-2 OS	WT
ATCC	CRL-1469	CVCL_0480	PANC-1	WT

Table 2: Summary of the GALC antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab240638**	1013689-11	AB_3101785	recombinant mono	EPR23598-126	rabbit	0.59	Wb
ABclonal	A23229**	6100001963	AB_3096861	recombinant mono	ARC58988	rabbit	1.14	Wb
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP3-32361**	H680010021	NA	recombinant mono	PSH03-45	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX101197	44510	AB_2037038	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.46	Wb
MilliporeSigma	MAB342*	3698122	AB_94857	monoclonal	mGALC	mouse	1.00	IF
Proteintech	11991-1-AP	00079717	AB_10641987	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.60	Wb, IP

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody, NA=not available

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	WT/KO cell mosaic	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody
WT KO	WT KO	WT KO	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	WT	WT	WT
WT	WT	WT	SM	SM	SM	KO	KO	KO
KO	KO	KO	UB	UB	UB			
IP	IP	IP	IP	IP	IP			
kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa	kDa			
245-	245-	245-	245-	245-	245-			
135-	135-	135-	135-	135-	135-			
75-	75-	75-	75-	75-	75-			
48-	48-	48-	48-	48-	48-			
25-	25-	25-	25-	25-	25-			
11-	11-	11-	11-	11-	11-			
Target protein detected (arrowhead)	Target protein detected (arrowhead) among others	Target protein not detected	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein captured in the IP	Target protein not captured in the IP	Target protein detected (white staining)	Target protein not detected	

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Figure 1: GALC antibody screening by western blot using knockdown in OCUM-1

Tissue type	Cell line	RNA score (log ₂ TPM + 1)
Pancreatic Cancer	AsPC-1	6.2
Gastric Cancer	OCUM-1	5.8
Pancreatic Cancer	SU.86.86	5.6
Brain Cancer	Daoy	4.2
Colon/Colorectal Cancer	HCT-15	3.9
Breast Cancer	MCF-7	3.6
Bone Cancer	U-2 OS	3.3
Pancreatic Cancer	PANC-1	2.7

Figure 2: GALC western blot on various cell lysates

Figure 3: GALC antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 4: GALC antibody screening by immunofluorescence

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: GALC antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of OCUM-1 WT and *GALC* KD were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated GALC antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KD lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab240638** at 1/500, A23229** at 1/1000, NBP3-32361** at 1/1000, GTX101197 at 1/500, MAB342* at 1/500 and 11991-1-AP at 1/500. Antibodies ab240638** and NBP3-32361** were titrated as the signal was too weak when following the supplier's recommendations. Predicted band size: 77 kDa. Observed bands: 74 kDa, 50 kDa and 26 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: GALC western blot in various cell lysates.

30 µg of lysates from the WT cell lines AsPC-1, OCUM-1, SU.86.86, Daoy, HCT-15, MCF7, U-2 OS and PANC-1 were processed for western blot. Anti-GALC A23229** was diluted at 1/1000 and GTX101197 at 1/500. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: GALC antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

OCUM-1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed overnight using 0.4 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated GALC antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with anti-GALC A23229** at 1/1000 or GTX101197 at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=5% starting material; UB=5% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitated; Wb=western blot, HC= antibody heavy chain, LC= antibody light chain. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 4: GALC antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

OCUM-1 WT and *GALC* KD cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KD cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on coverslips. Cells were stained with the indicated GALC antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KD) channels was performed. Representative images of the merged blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KD cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml, and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilutions used: ab240638** at 1/300, A23229** at 1/500, NBP3-32361** at 1/100, GTX101197 at 1/500, MAB342* at 1/600, 11991-1-AP at 1/300. Bars = 10 µm. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.